

tion can lead to the identification of interaction variables and constraints to production. In instances where new production practices evolve (such as the introduction of high-yielding semidwarf rice varieties), producer surveys may point to the need for a refinement of recommendations.

Producers can use the results to compare their farm responses with those of others. Identification of the principal sources of variation will allow producers to focus on information that can provide a basis for refining their production practices. Producers' knowledge of the relationship between

production inputs and rice quality can be improved if research and extension specialists report yield and quality results from research and experimental trials and if more research is devoted to producer-controlled impacts such as postharvest handling. ■

Comparing methods of stability analysis in rice hybrids

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Yield heterosis in rice is reported to interact with environment. Identifying rice hybrids with stable performance is a prerequisite to successfully exploiting this technology over a large area. The popular parameter for selection of stable entries used by many breeders is the varietal mean averaged over locations. Another method is to rank entries for each location and then use mean performance of the rank to assess their potential. It is well known that genotype \times environment ($G \times E$) interactions

in multilocal yield trials and the comparison of cultivar means are not very useful. In addition, the mean and its ranks do not indicate the location-wise magnitude of differences between the test entry and the standard check against which selection is to be made. In recent years, many new methods have been proposed for stability analysis. We compared the following three methods with selection based on the experimental mean: 1) a superiority measure of a cultivar, 2) nonparametric measures of phenotypic stability, and 3) relative yield as a measure.

We used the grain yield data of a hybrid rice trial conducted over 12 locations in the 1994 wet season for the study, and calculated the rank correlation (r_s) between methods. The results showed that selection based on means

of entries was closer to method 3, $r_s = 0.99$, followed by the superiority measure ($r_s = 0.95$). The ranking based on nonparametric measure was not related to the mean. Of the three methods used, the superiority measure was found to be useful for identifying stable hybrids. We analyzed the yield data from six trials conducted during 1994-95 to ascertain the usefulness of the superiority measure for identifying stable hybrids. The best-yielding hybrid was found to be the most stable. The superiority measure—as a method—is simple, convenient, and quite useful, because it uses only one parameter, which makes comparison among test genotypes easier. This method also indicates the highest yielding genotype, one that could be recommended for the whole region. ■

Education and communication

Role of voluntary agencies in popularizing hybrid rice production in India

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The Sri Aurobindo Institute of Rural Development, Gaddipalli, a nonprofit-oriented, nonsectarian, voluntary, and autonomous organization was established in 1973. A Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) was started in 1985 with

funds from the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR). This KVK was judged as the best among 261 KVKs in the country during 1994-95. Nalgonda District is in the southern Telangana zone of Andhra Pradesh. This is a rural district and 88% of the population depends on agriculture. Hybrid rice in China on a large scale proved to have a more than 25% yield advantage over conventional pureline varieties. The wide adaptability of rice hybrids has produced increased rice production and productivity in China since the mid-1980s. This success prompted ICAR to accelerate research on hybrid rice, through an ICAR-

UNDP-funded project in India. This research network project involved 12 research centers (two lead, seven associate, and three strategic centers) and state seed production agencies located in the target environment. Through this network, several rice hybrids were developed and released for commercial cultivation. To popularize hybrid rice production on a large scale, the Sri Aurobindo Institute developed an integrated project that involved adaptive research at the institute farm; on-farm testing in farmers' fields; layout demonstrations on hybrid rice seed production; production and distribution of good quality hybrid rice

seeds; training farmers, farm women, rural youth, and science graduates; organizing demonstrations in F_1 commercial seed production; popularizing hybrid rice technology through extension services; and producing multimedia training materials on hybrid rice technology. The important lesson we learned was that for each location and season, we needed to determine the seeding interval for the parental lines. During the past three seasons (1995-96), hybrid rice seed

production was carried out on 164 ha in farmers' fields. A total yield of 195 t of hybrid seeds was produced and supplied to various companies and individual farmers. This seed was enough for the commercial production of hybrid rice on 9,750 ha. During the 1996 wet season, hybrid rice seed production was carried out on 90 ha.

Training progressive farmers, youth, and farm women in hybrid rice seed production and F_1 commercial cultivation promotes hybrid rice cultivation

and increases rice yields. Training was organized in hybrid rice seed production for various categories of clients—farmers, farm women, farm youth, extension officers, and representatives of seed companies. More than 33,400 man-days of training were imparted during 1995-96. With the assistance of the United Nations Development Programme, this KVK organized a large-scale training program for farm women. ■

Socioeconomic impact

Economics of hybrid rice seed production in India

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Input-output data on hybrid seed production were obtained from seed growers' farms under private companies and a nongovernment organization (KVK, Gaddipally, Andhra Pradesh) from 1992-93 to 1994-95. Using these data, we studied the cost-return profile of F_1 seed production. The F_1 seed yield was only 560 kg ha⁻¹ when it was produced for the first time in 1992-93, but it increased to 1,385 kg ha⁻¹ in 1994-95. The average total cost of

F_1 seed production was Rs 23,840 ha⁻¹. Costs involved 45% for labor, 24% for manure and fertilizers, and 8% for gibberellic acid. The cost of 1 kg of seed produced dropped from Rs 33 (US\$0.92) in 1992-93 to Rs 17 (US\$0.48) during 1994-95, primarily because of increased yield. Because hybrid rice seed production is labor-intensive, 280-300 additional man-days of employment could be generated in the rural area, especially for women. In addition, gross and net returns to F_1 seed production are Rs 42,710 (US\$1,186) and Rs 18,870 (US\$524) ha⁻¹, respectively, at Rs 25 (US\$0.69) as the procurement price kg⁻¹. At the rate of the procurement price paid to seed growers by the seed industry, however, the computed

economically viable threshold seed yield was 1,900 kg ha⁻¹. If F_1 seed production is to be made economically viable to seed growers at 1,385 kg ha⁻¹ of seed yield, the procurement price should be Rs 34 (US\$0.95) kg⁻¹. The ratio of seed (F_1) area to commercial cultivation area of hybrid rice is estimated at 1:37.6. Thus, close to 53,000 ha are needed for an F_1 seed production program to meet the seed requirement of 2 million ha under hybrid rice by the year 2000. Our results stress the need to further improve F_1 seed yields. We also need to formulate an incentive-oriented and forward-contract base price policy for F_1 seed to induce seed growers to produce the required hybrid rice seed. ■

Impact of hybrid rice on India's food economy: implications and policy issues

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Basic data from the literature on the nature and impact of the adoption of hybrid rice in China and experiences in other research centers were gathered. Additional supporting data were collected from farmers' fields in the major rice-growing states in India

where rice hybrids were released recently. All these data formed the basis for this study. Hybrid rice outyields existing conventional high-yielding varieties by 1-2 t ha⁻¹ in irrigated environments. The adoption of hybrid rice would shift the production function farther upward and the increased rice output in irrigated areas would result in a higher domestic supply. In the short run, this could lead to a further widening of the income inequalities between irrigated and unirrigated regions. In addition, hybrid rice would benefit large farmers, who are early adopters with an ability to

purchase costly hybrid rice seed every crop season. A long-term use of this technology, however, would benefit the entire rice-farming community and urban population as well. Hybrid rice technology would generate a more marketable surplus. As a consequence, higher domestic prices of rice would be prevented in the consumer market, which would benefit urban consumers, especially low and middle class groups. Hybrid rice would also add to central buffer stocks and increase the supply of rice through the public distribution system at cheaper prices. Because hybrid rice technology is labor-